

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VITAMIN D3 DEFICIENCY AND HIGH BLOOD SUGAR

*Saja Abdel Hamza Daher, Abbas Nasser Jassim, Dalia Kakarine Abdul Kadhim,
Hussein Saad Abdulzahra*

Department of Medical physics, College of Science, University of AL_Mustaqbal

Abstract: Diabetes is a chronic (long-lasting) health condition that affects how your body turns food into energy. Particularly, diabetes during pregnancy including type 1, type 2, or gestational diabetes can negatively affect the health of women and their babies. It is now recognized that there are a variety of calcium metabolic disorders that are related to defects in the synthesis and metabolism of vitamin D. In current study, it has been found that Vitamin D3 levels measured in the same subjects were lower in diabetes compare to control. Further analysis showed that low levels of Vitamin D3 were detected in pregnant female with diabetes compare to non-pregnant diabetes female. This result may be explained by the fact that low level of D3 can increase blood sugar in pregnant female.

Introduction

Diabetes is a chronic disease that occurs either when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin it produces. Insulin is a hormone that regulates blood sugar. (World Health Organization 10 November 2021): There are three main types of diabetes - type 1, type 2, and gestational. Type 1 diabetes can affect people of any age, but it usually occurs in children or young adults. People with type 1 diabetes need daily insulin injections to control blood sugar levels. (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 20/3/2020). Type 2 diabetes is the most common type of diabetes, accounting for about 90% of all cases of diabetes. It is generally characterized by insulin resistance, in which the body does not fully respond to insulin. Because insulin doesn't work properly, blood glucose levels keep rising, releasing more insulin. (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020). Gestational diabetes is associated with multiple negative pregnancy outcomes. Women with gestational diabetes later run the risk of developing type 2 diabetes, especially three to six years after giving birth. Exposure to hyperglycaemia in utero also puts children at a high risk of developing overweight or obesity associated with the development of type 2 diabetes. (International Diabetes federation 7\1\2020). Vitamin D is one of the four fat-soluble vitamins (vitamin A, E, and K). It is stored and dissolved in your fatty tissues instead of water, and the benefit of this is that it can be stored in your body for long periods of time. (Worldwide shipping from the USA and UK TESToFUEL November 16, 2017). Vitamin D3 is necessary for the normal functioning of many body systems. Vitamin D3 deficiency has been associated with many symptoms and conditions: fibromyalgia, chronic fatigue disease, osteoporosis, kidney disease. Cardiovascular disease, asthma, cancer. (Pittas *et.al.*2007). Research shows that more than a billion people worldwide are deficient in vitamin D. Symptoms include: muscle weakness and pain, weak bones, fatigue, inflammation, and hair loss. A deficiency may lead to many health conditions, such as: depression, hypertension (high blood pressure), arthritis, and eczema. Therefore, a simple blood test can check vitamin

D levels. (Yvette Stines *et.al.* 2021 Medically reviewed by Meredith Bull, ND). Low levels of vitamin D are a prevalent issue in people with and without diabetes across the globe. Research has repeatedly found a clear association between low vitamin D levels in patients with insulin resistance and a high risk of developing type 2 diabetes as shown in 2011 study from Canada. (Health News 25-7-2019) —This newest study appears to show that with supplementation prior to diagnosis, or soon after, the body retains the ability to respond better on the cell level to insulin, which counters the hallmark of type 2 diabetes — insulin resistance,|| Jennifer Smith, CDE, RD, told Healthline. (Jennifer Smith *et.al.* 2019).

The other thing it appears to help with is allowing the beta cells in the pancreas that make insulin to stay healthy and functional,|| added Smith, who treats patients with all types of diabetes across the globe at Integrated Diabetes Services. (Health News 25-7-2019). Beta cells play a central role in insulin secretion. Gradual beta cell dysfunction is the biggest culprit of type 2 diabetes for approximately 60 percent of people diagnosed, according to a 2016 study published in *Diabetes Care*. (Health News 25-7-2019). The remaining 40 percent, then, is potentially able to reverse the condition through significant changes in nutrition, exercise, and body weight. (Health News 25-7-2019). Aim and Objectives: The project aimed to study the level of vitamin D3 in diabetes patients. Followed by objectives:

1. To learn how to collect blood samples from diabetes patients.
2. To estimate level of vitamin D3 and blood sugar.
3. To understand Elisa technique.
4. To analyses result data.

Diabetes is a chronic disease that occurs either when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin it produces. Insulin is a hormone that regulates blood sugar (Fig. 1- 1). Hyperglycaemia, or raised blood sugar, is a common effect of uncontrolled diabetes and over time leads to serious damage to many of the body's systems, especially the nerves and blood vessels (Fig. 1-2). (World Health Organization 10 November 2021).

Figure (1-1) Insulin producing cells

Figure (1- 2) Levels of insulin hormone in blood

There are three main types of diabetes – type 1, type 2 and gestational. Type 1 diabetes around 10% of all people with diabetes has type 1 diabetes. This type of diabetes is caused by an autoimmune reaction where the body's defense system attacks the cells that produce insulin. As a result, the body produces very little or no insulin. The exact causes of this are not yet known, but are linked to a combination of genetic and environmental conditions. (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 20/3/2020). Type 1 diabetes can affect people at any age, but usually develops in children or young adults. People with type 1 diabetes need daily injections of insulin to control their blood glucose levels. If people with type 1 diabetes do not have access to insulin, they will die. (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 20/3/2020). The risk factors for type 1 diabetes are still being researched. However, having a family member with type 1 diabetes slightly increases the risk of developing the disease. Environmental factors and exposure to some viral infections have also been linked to the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 20/3/2020). Symptoms of type 1 diabetes: The most common symptoms of type 1 diabetes include: Abnormal thirst and dry mouth, sudden weight loss, frequent urination, Lack of energy, tiredness, constant hunger, blurred vision and bedwetting. (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 20/3/2020). Diagnosing type 1 diabetes can be difficult so additional tests may be required to confirm a diagnosis. People with type 1 diabetes require daily insulin treatment, regular blood glucose monitoring and a healthy lifestyle to manage their condition effectively (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 20/3/2020). Type 2 diabetes is the most common type of diabetes, accounting for around 90% of all diabetes cases. It is generally characterized by insulin resistance, where the body does not fully respond to insulin. Because insulin cannot work properly, blood glucose levels keep rising, releasing more insulin. For some people with type 2 diabetes this can eventually exhaust the pancreas, resulting in the body producing less and less insulin, causing even higher blood sugar levels (hyperglycaemia). (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020). Additionally, it is most commonly diagnosed in older adults, but is increasingly seen in children, adolescents and younger adults due to rising levels of obesity, physical inactivity and poor diet. The cornerstone of type 2 diabetes management is a healthy diet, increased physical activity and maintaining a healthy body weight. Oral medication and insulin are also frequently prescribed to help control blood glucose levels. (International Diabetes federation Covid-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020). Risk factor Several risk factors have been associated with type 2 diabetes and include: Family history of diabetes, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, Increasing age, High blood pressure, Ethnicity, Impaired glucose tolerance (IGT), History of gestational diabetes and Poor nutrition during pregnancy.

(International Diabetes federation Coved-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020). Changes in diet and physical activity related to rapid development and urbanisation have led to sharp increases in the numbers of people living with type 2 diabetes. The symptoms of type 2 diabetes are similar to those of type 1 diabetes, in addition to: Slow healing wounds, recurrent infections in the skin and tingling or numbness in hands and feet. These symptoms can be mild or absent and so people with type 2 diabetes may live several years with the condition before being diagnosed. (International Diabetes federation Coved-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020): Management of type 2 diabetes: The cornerstone of managing type 2 diabetes is a healthy lifestyle, which includes a healthy diet, regular physical activity, not smoking, and maintaining a healthy body weight. (International Diabetes federation Coved-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020). Over time, a healthy lifestyle may not be enough to keep blood glucose levels under control and people with type 2 diabetes may need to take oral medication. If treatment with a single medication is not sufficient, combination therapy options may be prescribed. (International Diabetes federation Coved-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020). When oral medication is not sufficient to control blood glucose levels, people with type 2 diabetes may require insulin injections. The most commonly used oral medications for type 2 diabetes include: Metformin and Sulfonylureas. (International Diabetes federation Coved-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020). Gestational diabetes: Gestational diabetes is associated with multiple adverse pregnancy outcomes. Women with gestational diabetes are at subsequent high risk of type 2 diabetes, especially three to six years after delivery. Also, exposure to hyperglycaemia in the womb predisposes children to a high risk of becoming overweight or obese, associated with the development of type 2 diabetes. Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a severe and neglected threat to maternal and child health. Many women with GDM experience pregnancy-related complications including high blood pressure, large birth weight babies and obstructed labour. Approximately half of women with a history of GDM go on to develop type 2 diabetes within five to ten years after delivery. The prevalence of high blood glucose (hyperglycaemia) in pregnancy increases rapidly with age and is highest in women over the age of 45. (International Diabetes federation 7\1\2020). Random Blood Sugar (RBS) Test

A random blood sugar test is a test carried out to measure the levels of glucose in your blood. Glucose – It is a carbohydrate belonging to the class of monosaccharides. In fact, it is the amplest monosaccharide. It is a simple sugar and its name is derived from the ancient Greek word gleukos which means —sweet delightful wine. Plants manufacture glucose during photosynthesis with the assistance of energy from the sun. (FACTDr), Factual research, Healthy living, Last Updated December 20th 2021). Our body needs glucose as the principal source of energy. It is derived from the food we eat. Heart, brain, kidneys, and muscles are among a few principal organs of our body that are dependent on a constant supply of glucose to function

optimally (FACTDr , Factual research . Healthy living , Last Updated December 20th 2021). Fasting Blood Sugar Levels

Fasting, as the name suggest, means refraining from eating of drinking any liquids other than water for eight hours. It is used as a test for diabetes. After fasting, a carbohydrate metabolism test is conducted which measures blood glucose levels. During fasting, the hormone glucagon is stimulated and this increases plasma glucose levels in the body. If a patient does not have diabetes, their body will produce insulin to rebalance the increased glucose levels. (Diabetes.co.uk, Editor on January 15, 2019 last reviewed January 7, 2022). However people with diabetes either do not produce enough insulin to rebalance their blood sugar (typically in type 1 diabetes) or their body is not able to use the insulin effectively enough (typical of type 2 diabetes). (Diabetes.co.uk , Editor on january 15, 2019 last reviewed january 7, 2022) Consequently, when blood glucose levels are tested, people with diabetes will have blood sugar levels significantly higher than people who do not have diabetes. (Diabetes.co.uk , Editor on january 15, 2019 last reviewed january 7, 2022) , What is the fasting blood sugar test used for?

The fasting blood sugar test is also used to test the effectiveness of different medication or dietary changes on people already diagnosed as diabetic. (Diabetes.co.uk, Editor on january 15, 2019 last reviewed january 7, 2022). Fasting test results: The results of a fasting test with respect to glucose levels in the body are as follows: * Normal: 3.9 to 5.4 mmols/l (70 to 99 mg/dl), Prediabetes or Impaired: Glucose Tolerance: 5.5 to 6.9 mmol/l (100 to 125 mg/dl) and diagnosis of diabetes: 7.0 mmol/l (126 mg/dl) or above (Diabetes.co.uk Editoron January 15 2019 last reviewed january 7, 2022). Vitamin D is one of four fat-soluble vitamins (the others being vitamin A,E and K). It is stored and dissolved in your fatty tissue rather than in water, the benefit of this being that it can store in your body for long periods of time. Where vitamin D differs from other nutrients though is it's not technically a vitamin – it's a hormone produced from cholesterol when your body is exposed to the ultraviolet rays of the sun. (Worldwide shipping from the USA and UK TESToFUEL November 16, 2017). The sixth steroid hormone Vitamin D is often referred to as a steroid hormone because it has a potent effect on other hormones. In the research you'll often find it labelled as a secosteroid, purely due to its action on the endocrine system. It acts kind of like a chaperone, guiding nutrients into manufacturing other important hormones. (Worldwide shipping from the USA and UK TESToFUEL November 16, 2017). There are two forms of the nutrient: Ergocalciferol – D2 and Cholecalciferol – commonly referred to as D3. Vitamin D3 it's much more bioavailable than ergocalciferol – in fact, taking a D2 dose can actually reduce D3 levels. (Worldwide shipping from the USA and UK TESToFUEL [Holick, MF et al. Evaluation, treatment, and prevention of vitamin D deficiency: an endocrine society clinical practice guideline. JCEM. 2011; 96(7): 1911-1930]) Signs and Symptoms: Vitamin D3 is necessary for normal

functioning in many of the body's systems. Deficiencies in D3 have been associated with several symptoms and conditions: Firstly, Fibromyalgia and Chronic Fatigue Disease – Generalized muscle pain and symptoms like bone pain and unexplained muscle weakness might be a sign of vitamin D3 deficiency. Often, these symptoms are mistaken for fibromyalgia and chronic fatigue disease, and both of these conditions have been shown to have a high correlation with D3 deficiency with up to 70% of sufferers testing low in D3. Secondly, Osteoporosis – In addition to generalized muscle and bone pain, actual demineralization of bone can occur when deficiencies in vitamin D3 interfere with proper calcium absorption. Bones can become brittle and fractures may occur, especially in older people (Pittas et.al.2007). Thirdly, Kidney Disease – Those with chronic kidney disease should be checked for low vitamin D3 levels, as studies show impaired renal activity results in decreased conversion to D3 (Fig 1-3). Fourthly, Cardiovascular Disease – Studies have shown a high correlation between higher risk of cardiovascular disease and vitamin D3 deficiencies. Anyone with cardiovascular disease should be tested to ensure they are at normal D3 levels. Fifthly, Asthma – An increase in the symptoms of asthma are also associated with D3 deficiencies, especially in children. Asthma sufferers in the northern climates tend to suffer more symptoms during the winter months from cold, and potentially from the lower levels of D3 resulting from lower levels and duration of sunlight. Eventually, Cancer – Vitamin D3 offers protection against several types of cancer including colon, breast, ovarian and prostate cancers. Vitamin D3 inhibits tumor growth and the proliferation of cancer cells. Cancer rates have been shown to be 67% higher among those with low levels of vitamin D3. (Natural Wellness stephen Holt, MD, PhD, FACP , May 27th 2016).

Figure (1-3) Sign of vitamin D3 deficiency on muscles

Vitamin D3 has been known for its relationship with calcium absorption and bone health for years, and more recently has been shown to support health in a much wider range of body systems (Natural Wellness stephen Holt, MD ,phD, FACP , May 27th 2016). Vitamin D is important for a good overall health and it plays an important role in making sure our muscles, heart, lungs and brain function well. And it is required for strong immune system. (Healthy and Natural World by jenny Hills, Nutritionist and Medical Writer 2020/3/16). Our body can make its own vitamin D from sunlight but many people have low levels during winter. It can also get vitamin D from supplements, and a very small amount comes from a few foods you eat, such as some fish, fish liver oils, egg yolks and in fortified dairy, cereals and grain products, which makes vitamin D unique compared to other vitamins is that your body can make its own vitamin D when you expose your skin to sunlight, whereas you need to get other vitamins from the foods you eat. (Healthy and Natural World By jenny Hills, Nutritionist and Medical Writer 2020/3/16). Get vitamins D from the sun Finding out how long to stay in the sun in order to produce enough amounts of vitamin D can be very tricky and is different for every person, hence there isn't one recommendation for everyone. The reason for that is that the amount of time you need to spend in the sun for your skin to make enough vitamin D depends on a number of factors, such as how

dark your skin is or how easily you get sunburnt, the thickness of the ozone layer, the time of the year and what time of day it is. It is believed that short daily period of sun exposure without sunscreen (about 10-15 minutes for lighter-skinned people) during the summer months is enough for most people to make enough vitamin D. (Healthy and Natural World By Jenny Hills, Nutritionist and Medical Writer 2020/3/16). Evidence suggests that the most effective time of day for vitamin D production is between 11am and 3pm. The larger the area of skin that is exposed to sunlight, the more chance there is of making enough vitamin D before you starts to burn. (Healthy and Natural World By Jenny Hills, Nutritionist and Medical Writer 2020/3/16). The most common Causes of Lack of Vitamin D: Firstly, limited exposure to sunlight – Some of us live in northern latitudes, wear long clothes, or have a job that is taken place mostly indoors. Also sunscreen inhibits vitamin D production. Dark skin – People with dark skin have higher levels of melanin, and this pigment reduces the skin's ability to make vitamin D when exposed to sunlight. Secondly, Kidney and liver function – These organs play an important role in converting vitamin D to its active form, so kidney or liver diseases can reduce the ability of these organs to create biologically active form of vitamin D in the body. Thirdly, strict vegetarian diet – Food sources that contain vitamin D are mostly animal-based, such as fish and fish oils, egg yolks, cheese, fortified milk and beef liver. Fourthly, digestive problems – Certain medical conditions, such as Crohn's disease, cystic fibrosis, and celiac disease can reduce the ability of the intestines to absorb vitamin D from food. Finally, obesity – Obesity may cause low vitamin D levels. Research suggests that vitamin D may become 'trapped' inside fat tissue so less of it is available in our blood circulation. (Healthy and Natural World By Jenny Hills, Nutritionist and Medical Writer 2020/3/16). Vitamin D Deficiency Related Diseases and Conditions Researchers are still working to fully understand how vitamin D works within our body and how it affects our overall health, but it is believed to be a link between vitamin D deficiency to quite a number of ailments: Osteoporosis – An adequate amounts of calcium and vitamin D are important for maintaining bone density and strength. A lack of vitamin D causes calcium-depleted bone, which further weakens the bones and increases the risk of fractures. Asthma – Vitamin D deficiency is linked to lower lung functions and worse asthma control, especially in children. Vitamin D may improve asthma control by blocking inflammation-causing proteins in the lung, as well as increasing production of another protein which has anti-inflammatory effects. Heart health – Vitamin D deficiency may be linked to a higher risk of high blood pressure (hypertension) as well as increased risk of death from cardiovascular disease. Inflammation – It has been found that vitamin D deficiency is associated with inflammation, a negative response of the immune system. Vitamin D deficiency has been linked to a number of inflammatory diseases, including rheumatoid arthritis, lupus, inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and type 1 diabetes. Cholesterol – Vitamin D regulates cholesterol levels in the blood: it has been shown that without adequate sun exposure, vitamin D precursors turn to cholesterol instead of vitamin D. Allergies – Studies show that children who had lower levels of vitamin D are more likely to have multiple food allergies. Influenza – Some studies showed a link between lack of vitamin D and common respiratory infections, and indicate that people with the lowest vitamin D levels report having significantly more cases of cold and flu than those with higher levels. Depression – Vitamin D deficiency is linked to depression: receptors for vitamin D are present on many areas of the brain and are involved in numerous brain processes, making it likely that this vitamin might be associated with depression and that vitamin D supplements might play an important role in treating depression. Type-2 Diabetes – Studies have demonstrated correlations between low vitamin D levels and the development of type 2 diabetes. Different studies provide evidence that vitamin D may contribute to glucose tolerance through its effects on insulin secretion and insulin sensitivity. Oral health – Several recent reports demonstrate a significant association between periodontal health and the intake of vitamin D. Also elderly patients with low vitamin D levels have a higher rate of tooth loss than those with high vitamin D levels. Rheumatoid arthritis – Low vitamin D may play a role in developing rheumatoid arthritis. Studies have found that women who get more vitamin D seem less likely to get rheumatoid arthritis. Also among people who already have rheumatoid arthritis, those with low vitamin D levels tend to have more active symptoms. Cancer – Vitamin D deficiency may be linked to cancer: a certain study indicated that more than 75% of people with a variety of cancers have

low levels of vitamin D, and the lowest levels are associated with more advanced cancers. However additional research is required to determine whether higher vitamin D levels are related to lower cancer incidence or death rates. (Healthy and Natural World By Jenny Hills, Nutritionist and Medical Writer 2020/3/16). The recommended daily amount of vitamin D is 600 IU for adults under 70 and 800 IU for those over 70. Foods with high amounts include many kinds of fish and fortified milk and cereal. Supplements are the most reliable way to maintain vitamin D levels. Sunlight increases vitamin D production in your body. But it's impossible to know how much it contributes. D3 Deficiency: Research shows more than a billion people worldwide have a vitamin D deficiency. Symptoms include: Muscle weakness and aches, Weak bones, Fatigue, Inflammation and Hair loss. The deficiency may lead to many health conditions, such as: Depression, Hypertension (high blood pressure), Arthritis and Eczema. So, a simple blood test can check vitamin D levels. (By Yvette Stines December 11, 2021 Medically reviewed by Meredith Bull, ND). A recent study published by the European Journal of Endocrinology set out to determine whether consistent vitamin D3 supplementation could improve insulin sensitivity in patients either newly diagnosed with type 2 diabetes or at high risk of developing the disease. Consisting of 96 randomized patients, the double-blind, placebo-controlled trial included giving patients 5,000 international units (IUs) daily for 6 months. —In individuals at high risk of diabetes or with newly diagnosed type 2 diabetes, vitamin D supplementation for 6 months significantly increased peripheral insulin sensitivity and β -cell function, suggesting that it may slow metabolic deterioration in this population, explained the recent report. However, past research has failed to find a benefit from vitamin D supplementation on insulin sensitivity. Prior to this most recent research, the largest study on vitamin D's effect on insulin sensitivity and secretion included dosages of 4,000 IUs for nearly three years. The results were unimpressive with only a 2 percent difference between the group that did develop type 2 diabetes and the group that did not. Researchers suggest past studies may have failed to prove the benefits of vitamin D supplementation due to variables including ethnicity, glucose tolerance, and vitamin D dosage and duration during the study. (Health News 25-7-2019) Vitamin D and Diabetes: Low levels of vitamin D are a prevalent issue in people with and without diabetes across the globe. Research has repeatedly found a clear association between low vitamin D levels in patients with insulin resistance and a high risk of developing type 2 diabetes as shown in 2011 study from Canada. (Health News 25-7-2019) —This newest study appears to show that with supplementation prior to diagnosis, or soon after, the body retains the ability to respond better on the cell level to insulin, which counters the hallmark of type 2 diabetes — insulin resistance, Jennifer Smith, CDE, RD, told Healthline. (Health News 25-7-2019). —The other thing it appears to help with is allowing the beta cells in the pancreas that make insulin to stay healthy and functional, added Smith, who treats patients with all types of diabetes across the globe at Integrated Diabetes Services. (Health News 25-7-2019). Beta cells play a central role in insulin secretion. Gradual beta cell dysfunction is the biggest culprit of type 2 diabetes for approximately 60 percent of people diagnosed, according to a 2016 study published in Diabetes Care. (Health News 25-7-2019). The remaining 40 percent, then, is potentially able to reverse the condition through significant changes in nutrition, exercise, and body weight. (Health News 25-7-2019). Effects of vitamin D on insulin secretion: Vitamin D can positively impact insulin secretion in several ways, Vitamin D enters the beta cell and interacts with several types of receptors, which bind together and essentially activate the insulin gene, increasing the synthesis of insulin. (Health News 25-7-2019). It's also believed that vitamin D helps beta cells survive in a person with diabetes — whose body is otherwise trying to gradually destroy those cells — by interfering with the effects of cytokines, which are produced by the immune system. (Health News 25-7-2019). Vitamin D also plays a critical role in regulating the body's use of calcium. And calcium actually plays a small but critical role in the secretion of insulin. If too little vitamin D impairs the body's ability to manage calcium levels, it inevitably impairs the body's ability to produce insulin. (Health News 25-7-2019). Improving insulin sensitivity through vitamin D: Through the same receptors associated with vitamin D's impact on insulin secretion, vitamin D stimulates receptors that affect insulin sensitivity. Through a complicated physiological process, the interaction and binding with these receptors actually increase the number of total insulin receptors present in the body. It's also believed that vitamin D improves insulin

sensitivity by activating other receptors that help regulate the metabolism of fatty acids within muscle and body fat. (Health News 25-7- 2019). Like vitamin D's relationship with calcium and insulin secretion, calcium's presence is essential for both muscle and fat's response to insulin, enabling the uptake of insulin and glucose. Without calcium, this cannot happen. And without vitamin D, there is no calcium. (Health News 25-7- 2019). For patients whose blood work reveals a vitamin D deficiency, larger doses — 4,000 daily or 50,000 IUs weekly — can be taken for short periods of time to improve vitamin D levels. (Health News 25-7-2019). ELISA Technique: The enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is a powerful method for detecting and quantifying a specific protein in a complex mixture. Originally described by Engvall and Perlmann (1971), the method enables analysis of protein samples immobilized in microplate wells using specific antibodies. ELISAs are typically performed in 96-well or 384-well polystyrene plates, which passively bind antibodies and proteins. It is this binding and immobilization of reagents that makes ELISAs easy to design and perform. Having the reactants of the ELISA immobilized to the microplate surface makes it easy to separate bound from non-bound material during the assay. This ability to use high-affinity antibodies and wash away non-specific bound materials makes ELISA a powerful tool for measuring specific analytes within a crude preparation.

Result and Discussion

Vitamin D plays a critical role in regulating the body's use of calcium. And calcium actually plays a small but critical role in the secretion of insulin. If too little vitamin D impairs the body's ability to manage calcium levels, it inevitably impairs the body's ability to produce insulin. (Health News 25-7-2019). Vitamin D can positively impact insulin secretion in several ways; Vitamin D enters the beta cell and interacts with several types of receptors, which bind together and essentially activate the insulin gene, increasing the synthesis of insulin. (Health News 25-7-2019). Through the same receptors associated with vitamin D's impact on insulin secretion, vitamin D stimulates receptors that affect insulin sensitivity. Through a complicated physiological process, the interaction and binding with these receptors actually increase the number of total insulin receptors present in the body. (Health News 25-7-2019). In current study, Vitamin D₃ levels measured in the same subjects were lower in diabetes compare to control, particularly in females, were unrelated to hypertension (Fig 3.1 and 3.2).

Figure (3.1) Comparison Hba1c between diabetes patient (Hba1c-P) and control (Hba1c-C).

Figure (3.2) Detection D3 level in diabetes patient D3-P and control D3-C by using Elisa technique. D3 was significantly decreased in D3-P compare to D3-C.

Another area of interest is vitamin D status during pregnancy and lactation and whether a pregnant woman's vitamin D status plays a role in the development of diabetes in her child. (Gregory et al. 2010).

Further analysis showed that low levels of Vitamin D3 were detected in pregnant female with diabetes compare to non-pregnant diabetes female (Fig. 3.3 and 3.4). This result may be explained by the fact that low level of D3 can increase blood sugar in pregnant female.

Figure (3.3) Comparison Hba1c between female with diabetes (Hba1c-G1) and pregnant diabetes female (Hba1c-G2). Hba1c slightly increased in (Hba1c-G2) compare to (Hba1c-G1)

Figure (3.4) Detection of D3 level in female with diabetes (D3-G1) and pregnant diabetic female (D3-G2) by using Elisa technique. Analysis shows significantly decreasing of D3 in (D3-G2) compare to (D3-G1)

Conclusion: Vitamin D status appears to play a role in the development and treatment of diabetes. It is possible that optimal levels of serum vitamin D may be different for people at risk for developing diabetes, those with diabetes, and those without diabetes. (Danescu *et.al.* 2009). Many people with diabetes are low in vitamin D (Pittas *et.al.* 2007). This is an important finding because vitamin D is known to help regulate insulin levels (Mitri, *et.al.* 2014). New studies have assessed if vitamin D supplementation helps in the management of type 2 diabetes (Wu C, Qiu S, Zhu X, *et.al.* 2017).

References

1. International Diabetes federation 7\1\2020.
2. FACTDr, Factual research. Healthy living, Last Updated December 20th 2021.
3. Pittas AG, Lau J, Hu FB, Dawson-Hughes B: The role of vitamin D and calcium in type 2 diabetes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Endo Metab* 92:2017–2029, 2007
4. Holick, MF. Evaluation, treatment, and prevention of vitamin D deficiency: an endocrine society clinical practice guideline. *JCEM*. 2011; 96(7): 1911-1930.
5. Healthy and Natural World by jenny Hills, Nutritionist and Medical Writer 2020/3/16.
6. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK555922>.
7. <https://www.bosterbio.com/protocol-and-troubleshooting/elisa-principle>.
8. Gregory JM, Lilley JS, Misfeldt AA, Buscariollo DL, Russell WE, and Moore DJ: Incorporating type 1 diabetes prevention into clinical practice. *Clinical Diabetes* 28:61–70, 2010
9. Danescu LG, Levy S, Levy J: Vitamin D and diabetes mellitus. *Endocr* 35:11–17, 2009
10. Mitri J, Pittas AG. Vitamin D and diabetes. *Endocrinol Metab Clin North Am*. 2014; 43(1):205-232. Doi: 10.1016/j.ect.2013.09.010.
11. Wu C, Qiu S, Zhu X, et al. Vitamin D supplementation and glycemic control in type 2 diabetes patients: A systematic review and meta- analysis. *Metabolism*. 2017; 73:67-76.

12. International Diabetes federation Coved-19 and diabetes 16/10/2020.
13. Diabetes.co.uk, Editor on January 15, 2019 last reviewed January 7, 2022.
14. Health News 25-7-2019.
15. International Diabetes federation Coved-19 and diabetes 20/3/2020.
16. Word Health Organization 10 November 2021.
17. By Yvette Stines December 11, 2021 Medically reviwed by Meredith Bull, ND.
18. Natural Wellness stephen Holt, MD ,phD, FACP , May 27th 2016.
19. doi: 10.1016/j.metabol.2017.05.005.